

A Study of the Personality Factors of the Teachers Working in Government / Aided Colleges and Self-Finance Colleges in Aligarh

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Abstract

The objectives of the present study was to study the personality factors of the Teachers working in Self-finance colleges and Government colleges in Aligarh. For the same, researcher formulated hypotheses, with the help of simple random sampling, researcher collected the sample of 225 teachers in which 125 from Government colleges and 100 teachers from Self-finance colleges. Researcher use 10 P.F. questionnaire to assess the personality factor which is very reliable and valid. The findings of the study indicates that both type of teacher show the average level of personality tests with individual difference.

Personality has been derived from the Latin word 'Persona' which means 'mask' used by actors to change their appearance. It is a combination of an Individual though, characteristics, behaviour, attitude, idea and habits. According to Ogburn and Nimkoff, "Personality is the totality of sentiments, attitudes, idea, habits, skills and behaviours of an individual."

Allport defined personality as "the dynamic organization within the individual of those psychophysical systems that determine his character behaviour and thoughts."

The sixteen personality factors questionnaire (16 PF) is a self report personality test developed over a several decades of empirical research by Raymond B. Cattell, Marice Tatsuoka and Herbert Eber. The sixteen PF provides a measure of normal personality and can also be used by psychologist, and other mental health professionals, as a clinical instrument to help diagnose psychiatrics disorders, as well as help with prognosis and therapy planning. The 16 PF instrument provides clinicians with a normal range measurement of anxiety, adjustment, emotional stability and behaviour problems. It can also be used within other areas of psychology, such as career and occupational selection.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the personality factors of the teachers working in Govt. / Aided colleges in Aligarh.
2. To study the personality factors of the teachers working in self finance colleges in Aligarh.
3. To compare the personality factors of the teachers working in govt. / aided colleges and self finance colleges in Aligarh.

Terminology of the Study

1. **Personality factors** : In the present study, personality factor means the sixteen personality factors given as the primary source traits covered by 16 PF. Test made by Cattell, H.B. (1989).
2. **Teachers** : In the present study 'Teacher' means a person who is working in a graduate / post graduate colleges possess M.Phil. / Ph.D. or U.G.C. N.E.T. as per UGC norms.
3. **Aided College** : In the present study, aided college means the graduate / post graduate college of Aligarh, affiliated with Dr. B.R.A. University Agra and they are getting the financial aid from State / Central Government.

4. **Self-Finance College :** In the present study, self – finance college means the graduate / post graduate colleges of Aligarh, affiliated to Dr. B.R.A. University Agra and they are not getting financial aid from the government depending on self generated funds.

Hypotheses of the Study

To achieve the objectives of the study, researcher formulated the following hypotheses :

1. The Standard Ten Score (STEN) obtain by the Teachers working in Govt. / aided colleges on the sixteen personality factor questionnaire will be ‘Average’.
2. The Standard Ten Score (STEN) obtain by the Teachers working in the self finance colleges on the Sixteen Personality factors questionnaire will be average.
3. There will be not significant difference in between the Standard Ten Score (STEN) on the sixteen personality factor questionnaire by the teachers working in govt/ aided and self finance colleges.

Population and Sample of the Study

The population of the present study comprises in all the teachers who are working in all govt/ aided and self finance colleges in Aligarh. To begin with, the researcher prepared a list of govt/ aided colleges and self-finance colleges of Aligarh. Then the researcher selected 10 colleges randomly wherein five govt/ aided and five are of self financed. In present study, 225 teachers constitute the sample of the study wherein 100 teachers selected from aided colleges and 125 teachers from self financed colleges.

Tool of the Study

The sixteen personality factor questionnaire designed by H.B. Cattell was adopted for this study. The test was designed for use with individuals age 16 and above. This test can be scored by manually as well as by use of computer as per situation. The test measure 16 functionally independent and psychologically meaningful dimensions of the personally.

Personality factors measured by the 16 P.F. are not just unique to the test but, instead rest within the context of a general theory of personality. In addition to the 16 primary factors, the test can be used as a measures of at least five secondary dimensions. The test is recognized as highly reliable and valid test.

Methodology

The present study is a form of descriptive survey which investigate the personality factors of the teachers working in govt./ aided and self financed colleges of Aligarh. Simple Random survey was used to collect the data from the sample.

Researcher firstly contacted to the target colleges to collect data. After rapport formation, researcher gave instruction to the subjects and ask to respond. After the completion of work, researcher collected question booklet and answer sheet. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher scored the responses as per instructions given in the manual.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

After scoring the responses, researcher tabulated and analyzed the data, mean, standard deviation of govt./ aided teachers and self-finance teachers are as given below in a table form:

Factors	Teacher of Aided / Govt. N = 125			Teachers of Self Finance College N = 125		
	Mean	Stress	S.D.	Mean	Stress	S.D.
A	20	5	6.70	18	4	6.03
B	16	6	3.60	17	7	3.90
C	36	6	9.30	29	4	7.93
E	30	7	8.86	19	4	7.79
F	25	5	7.06	26	5	8.09

Factors	Teacher of Aided / Govt. N = 125			Teachers of Self Finance College N = 125		
	Mean	Stress	S.D.	Mean	Stress	S.D.
G	28	6	6.70	24	5	5.60
H	32	6	8.50	23	5	9.43
I	23	6	7.00	20	5	9.06
L	14	5	7.08	13	5	6.93
M	26	6	6.90	23	5	7.63
N	19	5	8.30	22	6	6.20
O	24	6	10.20	14	4	9.30
Q1	17	6	6.23	18	6	8.66
Q2	24	8	5.01	16	5	4.90
Q3	23	5	7.25	26	6	7.90
Q4	19	5	6.90	25	6	7.30

After the calculation of mean and standard deviation, researcher calculated C.R. of two group (Teachers of Govt. / Aided colleges and Self Finance Colleges) the 't' value of each factor and its significant level are as given below in the table.

**A Test Comparison of Significance Level of two groups
Government / Aided and Self-Finance Teachers**

Factor	't' value	Level of significance
A	2.50	.01 significant
B	2.17	.01 significant
C	5.42	.05 significant
E	1.90	Not significant
F	1.05	Not significant
G	6.67	.05 significant
H	7.03	.05 significant
I	2.77	.05 significant
L	1.14	Not significant
M	1.33	Not significant
N	3.26	.05 significant
O	8.13	.05 significant
Q1	1.06	Not significant
Q2	12.90	.05 significant
Q3	1.35	Not significant
Q4	6.74	.05 significant

Interpretation of the data was made on the following basis:

1. To study the personality factors of the teachers working in govt. / aided colleges.
2. To study the personality factors of the teachers working in self-finance colleges.
3. To find out the significant difference among the personality factors (given in 16 PF) of the teachers working in govt./ aided and self finance colleges.

Study of Personality Factors of the Teachers working in Govt./ Aided Colleges

(1) The objective of present study was to find out the personality factors of govt./ aided colleges and self financed teachers. To study the personality factors, researcher calculated raw score and converted raw score to standard sten score. With the help of sten score which can explain each factor in behavioural term.

The teacher of government and aided colleges scored 5 standard sten score on 11 factors, 6 sten score on personality factors, 7 sten score on 1 factor and 8 sten score on 1 factor.

(2) To study the personality factors of teachers working in self financed colleges : as the objective of the study was to find out personality factors of the teachers working in Govt. / aided and self finance colleges.

To study the personality factors of the teachers of self finance colleges, researcher calculated raw score and converted to sten score with the help of sten score, that can be explain each personality in behavioural term. The teachers working in self finance colleges scored 5 on 7 personality factors, 6 sten score on 4 personality factors and 4 sten points on 4 personality factors.

(3) To study the significant difference in between the scores of teachers working in self finance colleges and govt./ aided colleges. To achieve the said objective the researcher calculated the mean and standard deviation of raw scores. With the help of mean and standard deviation researcher calculated 't' value in between the means of sixteen factors of both group. On six personality factor (E.F.L.M. Q1 and Q3) the 't' value found below 1.98, on two personality factor A and B, the 't' value found more than 1.98, and below 2.58, and on eight personality factor (C.G.H.I.N.O.Q₂ and Q₄) the 't' value found more than 2.58.

Conclusion of the Study

The objective of present study was to find out the personality factors of the teachers who are working in self finance colleges and govt./ aided colleges and find out the test comparison in between the persoanality of the teachers working in different type of colleges.

On the basis of analysis and interpretation of the data the researcher made conclusions as follows:

1. The teacher's who are working in aided and govt. colleges express the average sten score on 14 personality factor. The teachers are average in relation to sizethemia v/s affectothemia, less intelligent v/s more intelligent, less ego strength v/s higher ego strength, sober v/s happy go lucky, expedient v/s conscientious, shy v/s socially bold, tough minded and tender minded, trusting v/s suspicious, practical v/s imaginative, sentimental v/s shrewd, self assured v/s apprehensive, conservative v/s experimenting, undisciplined v/s controlled and relaxed v/s tense, and teachers of govt./ aided scored high sten score in submissiveness v/s dominance.
2. The teachers who are working in self finance colleges express the average sten score on 11 personality factors as sober v/s happy go luck, confident v/s conscientious, shy v/s socially bold, realistic v/s tendermind, trusting v/s suspicious, practical v/s imaginative, sentimental v/s shrewd, conservative v/s experimenting, group dependent v/s self sufficient, undisciplined v/s controlled, relaxed v/s tense and teachers scored below average in reserve v/s outgoing, less emotional intelligence v/s emotionally stable, and self assured v/s apprehensive.
3. The third objective of the study was to made a test comparison in between the scores of the teachers of self finance colleges and govt./ aided college teachers. The conclusion made by the researcher are as follows:
 - The scores of govt/ aided teachers and self finance colleges found not significant on 6 personality factors as – submissiveness v/s dominance, sober v/s happy go lucky, trusting v/s suspicious, practical v/s imaginative, conservative v/s experimenting, undisciplined v/s controlled. The scores of govt. / aided colleges and self finance colleges found significant on .01 level of confidence related 2 personality factors as – Reserved v/s outgoing, less intelligence v/s more intelligent.
 - The scores of govt./ aided teachers and self-finance college teachers found significant on .05 level related 8 personality factors as emotionally instable v/s emotionally stable, shy v/s socially bold, realistic v/s tender minded, expedient

v/s contentious, sentimental v/s shrewd, confident v/s depressive, group dependent v/s self sufficient, and relaxed v/s tense.

Discussion

As the objectives of the present study was to find out the personality factors of govt./aided college teachers and self finance college teachers in Aligarh and to find out the significant difference in between the scores of teachers of self finance colleges and govt./ aided college teachers.

The conclusion of the study made by the researcher on the basis of findings.

In the present study, on 10 personality factors, the government working teacher and self finance college teachers express average sten score. Average sten score states that the personality traits are at average level in both type of teachers. It is also indicate that the results of the study follows the normal distribution of the traits. On 'A' factor self finance college teachers secure below average marks that express that teachers are more reserved, detached and critical cool, working condition and pressure may create these of effect. On second factor B which is related to the level of intelligence shows that government working teachers have higher level of intelligence. To get a government jobs, there are a provision of examination which make a difference on the basis of intelligence. It may be the reason so that govt./ aided teachers score higher from self finance college teachers. The feeling of interdependency within the group in self finance teachers in comparison to govt./ aided teachers. The educational setup of self finance college may be a reason of this fact.

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